

Mesoscopic Finite Element Modelling of Woven Reinforcements Applied to Sheet Moulding Compound Forming Simulation

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SUMMARY

A sheet moulding compound consisting of a fibreglass woven fabric impregnated with a polyester thermoset resin is evaluated to form a complex automotive part. A mesoscopic finite element approach using a mesh of one-dimensional and two-dimensional elements is used to model the nonlinear mechanical behavior of the fabric during the forming process.

Keywords: Woven reinforcements, Modelling, Finite Element Analysis, Sheet Moulding Compound

INTRODUCTION

The compression moulding of Sheet Moulding Compounds (SMC) is a promising process for producing high-volume low-cost composites parts. The process consists of pressing a stack of sheets, containing a reinforcement and a thermoset resin, for several minutes in a heated mould to cure the resin and form the part. Sheets of unsaturated polyester resin combined with thickening agents and filled with chopped glass fibres are generally used. Typically, SMC sheets only partially cover the die and the applied pressure spreads the fibres and the resin to fill the mould. Continuous fibre reinforcements are typically not advised for SMC processing of complex 3D parts because this type of reinforcement has limited flow capabilities [1, 2].

In the last ten years, much progress has been made in the simulation of fabric reinforcement forming, in particular woven fabrics [3]. Woven fabrics can undergo large deformation via in-plane shearing, but the deformation is limited by the development of wrinkling and/or tearing of the fabric. With the use of simulation tools, the initial blank size can be determined and the potential areas where defects such as wrinkles and/or tears can be predicted. These simulation tools can also capture the final fibre orientations for each layer of fabric throughout the part. These new insights allow automotive manufacturers to consider the use of woven fabric reinforcements for SMC, and to take advantage of the mechanical properties that can be achieved by this process for structural automotive parts.

In this study, an SMC composed of a fibreglass woven fabric impregnated with a polyester resin is evaluated to form a relatively complex automotive part. The finite element model used for the simulation [4, 5] is first briefly described. Then, the characterization of the SMC material is presented. Shear frame testing, tensile testing of the yarns and friction testing were performed to determine material parameters for the

finite element model. Finally, the forming of an actual automotive part is simulated and discussed.

MODELING

In-plane shearing is the main deformation mode of woven materials, which implies that the orthotropic directions can change significantly during the forming process for a dual curvature surface. Conventional orthotropic shell elements are not suitable to model such large shear deformations. Various methods have been developed to address this issue including semi-discrete finite elements or nonorthogonal constitutive models based on continuum shells [3]. A simple means to solve this problem is to use a mesoscopic (discrete) model based on a pin-jointed trellis of one-dimensional (1-D) elements (beam or trusses) that will have the ability of capturing the changes in the orthotropic directions as the fabric shears to conform to the shape of the mould. In this study, a shell element with only shear stiffness, i.e. no in-plane tensile or compressive stiffness, is used to account for the shear behaviour of the fabric (Figure 1). The shear stiffness of this two-dimensional (2-D) element increases with increasing shear deformation. In addition, a nonlinear tensile behaviour accounting for the uncrimping of the yarns is used for the material model of the 1-D elements.

Figure 1: Mesoscopic modelling of a plane-weave using a combination 1-D and 2-D elements

Constitutive equations

Explicit finite element codes such as ABAQUS/Explicit allow for customized stress-strain relationships at each time step via a user-defined material subroutine [6]:

$$\Delta\sigma_{ij}^{t+1} = C_{ijkl} \cdot \Delta\varepsilon_{kl}^{t+\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\sigma_{ij}^{t+1}$ is the stress increment at time step $t+1$, C_{ijkl} is the constitutive matrix at time-step t , and $\Delta\varepsilon_{kl}^{t+\frac{1}{2}}$ is the midpoint strain increment from the solver. For 1-D elements, Equation (1) becomes:

$$\Delta\sigma_{11}^{t+1} = C_{11} \cdot \Delta\varepsilon_{11}^{t+\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where C_{11} is the tangent tensile modulus and is a function of the strain ε_{11} . This tangent modulus is easily deduced from experimental tensile stress-true strain data of the fabric yarns.

Two reference frames as depicted in Figure 2 are used to implement the shearing behaviour within the shell element. The e_i unit vectors define the local orthogonal reference frame that rotates with the material, and the g_i basis vectors form a nonorthogonal frame that follows the fibre directions.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the reference frames used

The in-plane shear behaviour of the woven fabric can be captured by:

$$\Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{12}^{t+1} = \tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12}) \cdot \Delta \gamma_{12}^{t+1/2} \quad (3)$$

with $\Delta \gamma_{12}^{t+1/2} = 2 \cdot \Delta \varepsilon_{12}^{t+1/2}$ (where γ_{12} and ε_{12} denote the engineering and tensorial shear strains, respectively), $\Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{12}^{t+1}$ is the shear-stress increment expressed in g_i and $\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12})$ is the tangent shear modulus. For this research, the tangent shear modulus was determined from experimental data.

This constitutive equation uses the strain increment $\Delta \varepsilon_{12}^{t+1/2}$ expressed in e_i as it is given by the finite element solver to the user-defined material subroutine. However, the stress increment obtained is expressed in terms of the g_i basis and needs to be returned to the finite element solver in the e_i basis at the end of the user-defined material subroutine's updating of the state of stress. The relationship between the stresses $\Delta \sigma_{ii}$ expressed in g_i and the stresses $\Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{ii}$ expressed in e_i is obtained from a geometric analysis of Figure 2 [7]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \sigma_{11} \\ \Delta \sigma_{22} \\ \Delta \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \cos^2(\alpha + \theta) & 2 \cdot \cos \alpha \cos(\alpha + \theta) \\ \sin^2 \alpha & \sin^2(\alpha + \theta) & 2 \cdot \sin \alpha \sin(\alpha + \theta) \\ \sin \alpha \cos \alpha & \sin(\alpha + \theta) \cos(\alpha + \theta) & \sin(2\alpha + \theta) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \\ \Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{22} \\ \Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where α is the angle between e_1 and g_1 and θ is the angle between g_1 and g_2 . These angles can be determined within the user subroutine via the deformation gradient tensor known at each increment.

The 1-D elements carry the stress in the g_1 and g_2 directions and consequently $\Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{11} = \Delta \tilde{\sigma}_{22} = 0$ within the 2-D element. Thus, the stress increments are returned to the solver in the e_i basis using:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\sigma_{11} &= 2.\cos\alpha\cos(\alpha+\theta).\Delta\tilde{\sigma}_{12} \\
\Delta\sigma_{22} &= 2.\sin\alpha\sin(\alpha+\theta).\Delta\tilde{\sigma}_{12} \\
\Delta\sigma_{12} &= \sin(2\alpha+\theta).\Delta\tilde{\sigma}_{12}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

To be consistent with finite element codes that use the logarithmic strains for the summation of the strains increments, the logarithmic definition of strains should be used to determine $\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12})$ from the experimental data. The true or “logarithmic” shear angle γ^L can be obtained from the logarithmic strains in the principal stretch directions ε_I^L and ε_{II}^L by a 45° Mohr’s circle transformation. In the case of a shear frame test, a geometrical analysis leads to the expression of γ^L as a function of the geometric shear angle γ :

$$\gamma^L = \varepsilon_I^L - \varepsilon_{II}^L = -\ln(\tan(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\gamma}{2})) \tag{6}$$

The shear stress $\tilde{\sigma}_{12}$ is equal to the normalized shear force F_{sh} [8-10] divided by the thickness of the fabric. Finally, $\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma^L)$ is obtained from a derivation of $\tilde{\sigma}_{12}$ versus γ^L experimental shear frame test data.

Implementation

This approach can be set up in an explicit finite element code via a user-defined material subroutine. The ABAQUS/Explicit code has been chosen for the current study. The most suitable elements for the forming simulation of three dimensional (3-D) parts have been determined to be the continuum S4R shell and the B31 beam [5]. Either a square or a circular cross section can be used with the beams. The modelling approach has been validated by comparing experimental and simulation data for shear-frame and bias-extension tests that show a good agreement [4, 5].

FABRIC CHARACTERIZATION

An SMC material, composed of a fibreglass woven fabric impregnated with an uncured thermoset resin is considered. Tensile and shear-frame testing of the fabric were performed to characterize the fabric behaviour and to conclude material parameters for the user-defined material subroutine. Friction testing was also conducted to evaluate the fabric/tool friction coefficient.

Tensile testing

Uniaxial tensile testing was performed on an INSTRON 4464 machine with a 2-kN load cell. Pneumatic cord and yarn grips were used, and the gauge length was set to approximately one meter to minimize the effect of the deformation in the grips. The displacement rate was 5 mm/s. As the temperature and the uncured resin are not believed to affect the yarn tensile properties, yarns extracted from the dry fabric were tested at room temperature.

The modulus of the yarns determined from the slope of the load/true-strain curves. The effective section of the yarn A_{eff} has been considered. It has been determined to be 0.7 mm^2 from the linear density ρ_{linear} of the yarn and the fiberglass density ρ_{glass} ($A_{eff} = \rho_{linear} / \rho_{glass}$). In addition, measurements of the crimp ratio (i.e. difference between the length of the yarn and the length of the fabric) were performed. The results, presented in Table 1, can be used to assess the stress-true strain behaviour of the yarn within the fabric via an extrapolation of the decrimping [8]. Finally, a curve fit and a derivative lead to the tangent tensile moduli presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Yarn tensile properties

Yarn	Modulus (GPa)	Max. load (N)	Max stress (MPa)	Crimp ratio (%)
Warp/Weft	58.7±2.1	396±52	566±74	0.3/0.4

Table 2 : Tangent tensile moduli $C_{11}(\varepsilon_{11})$ for the yarns

Yarn	True strain ε_{11}	Tangent Modulus C_{11} (MPa)
Warp	$0 < \varepsilon_{11} < 0.004$	$9.22 \times 10^{11} \varepsilon_{11}^3$
	$0.004 < \varepsilon_{11}$	58700
Weft	$0 < \varepsilon_{11} < 0.0053$	$3.89 \times 10^{11} \varepsilon_{11}^3$
	$0.0053 < \varepsilon_{11}$	58700

Shear frame testing

In-plane shear behaviour could be influenced if the resin viscosity varies with temperature. Shear frame tests were conducted at 20°C and 50°C on the prepreg fabric using an INSTRON 4464 tensile machine. Higher temperatures have not been used because within the time needed to bring the fabric to temperature and the testing time (around 20-30 minutes total), the resin starts to cure. The shear-frame test procedure involved [8]:

- The specimen geometry was a cross with the cross yarns removed in the arms,
- The length of the frame L_F was 216 mm, and the length of the fabric L_f was 120 mm,
- The shear rate was 2 mm/s
- A mechanical conditioning consisting of five pre-test shears was done to reduce the effect of undesired tension that could arise from a misalignment of the yarns [8, 11, 12].

The normalized shear force F_{sh} and the shear angle γ were determined from the crosshead displacement δ and the total load on the frame F by the following equations [11]:

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \cdot \arccos\left(\frac{\delta}{2 \cdot L_F} + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$F_{sh} = \frac{L_F}{L_f^2} \frac{F}{2 \cos(\pi/4 - \gamma/2)} \quad (9)$$

Three tests were conducted at each temperature, and the results were similar for both temperatures. The shear force-shear angle curve obtained at 20°C is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Normalized shear force vs. shearing angle for room temperature (20°C) shear frame tests. The error bars represent one standard deviation.

The corresponding tangent shear modulus, $\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12})$, has been determined using logarithmic strains and the thickness of the cured fabric, i.e. 0.4 mm:

$$\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12}) = 22.08|\gamma_{12}|^4 - 44.63|\gamma_{12}|^3 + 32|\gamma_{12}|^2 - 8.57|\gamma_{12}| + 0.73 \quad (10)$$

$\tilde{C}_{33}(\gamma_{12})$ is expressed in MPa and γ_{12} in radians.

Friction testing

A load-control friction test apparatus was used to capture the static and dynamic coefficients of friction at the tool/fabric interface. The sample is clamped in a holder and compressed between two heated platens. The apparatus uses an active control system to maintain a prescribed normal force on the test sample. A DC motor drives a rack and pinion to pull the sample through the platens, and a tensile load cell measures the pull-out force F (Figure 3). The effective coefficient of friction, μ_{eff} , is calculated by

$$\mu_{eff} = \frac{F}{2N} \quad (11)$$

where the normal force N is multiplied by a factor of two to account for the two contacting surfaces on each side of the sample.

Figure 3: Schematic of the friction test apparatus.

The coefficient of friction is plotted versus the pull-out displacement. Typically, these curves result in an initial peak, followed by a drop and then a relatively flat response. The peak and “flat” portions of the curves correspond to the static and dynamic coefficients of friction, respectively [13]. Tool/fabric friction was characterized at 150°C , i.e. the tool temperature. The measured tool/fabric dynamic friction coefficient was 0.015 ± 0.005 . The friction was very low because of a significant lubricating action of the uncured thermoset resin.

FORMING SIMULATION OF AN ACTUAL PART

Forming simulations of an actual automotive part were performed. The model used the material parameters derived from the experimental characterization of the fabric. Two different fabric orientations were studied, i.e. $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ and $\pm 45^{\circ}$.

The size of the unit cell (UC) of the fabric is $5.1\text{ mm} \times 7.3\text{ mm}$. To simulate the draping of the large part considered in this research, the number of 1-D elements in each direction was set to be half the actual number of yarns to have a reasonable computation time. The size of the shell elements became $10.2\text{ mm} \times 14.6\text{ mm}$, and the cross section of the yarns was 1.4 mm^2 to ensure an unchanged fabric tensile stiffness. The meshes used for the fabric and the tools are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Cut view of the meshes used for the forming simulation.

The simulation results are analysed in terms of the shear-angle and yarn tension—two critical parameters for fabric forming. The simulations show that there is a preferential orientation of the fabric for the forming of this part. It can be seen in Figure 5 that the $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ orientation leads to very high shearing angles (above 60°) in the corners of the tub which will probably result in local wrinkling of the fabric, even for a very loose weaving like the one chosen [14]. In contrast, the $\pm 45^{\circ}$ orientation gives a more uniform distribution of the shearing than the $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ orientation and thereby minimizes the high shearing zones across the part.

Figure 5: SMC draping simulation. Shear angle contour in degrees
 (a) $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ orientation. (b) $\pm 45^{\circ}$ orientation.

The simulations also give insight to the tension in the yarns via the beam elements. The contour of the tension in the beam trellis is depicted in Figure 6 for the $\pm 45^{\circ}$ orientation. The yarn fracture load (~ 400 N, red contour) is reached in the bottom of the tub, probably due to the presence of numerous ribs. The $90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ orientation studied also exhibits very high yarn tension in the same zone. Yarn tearing is thus expected in these zones. However, a pre-forming operation for these areas would help to reduce the tension in the yarns.

Figure 6: SMC draping simulation. $\pm 45^{\circ}$ orientation. Yarn tension contour (N).

Because this forming method is a closed-mould process, the fabric blank has to be precisely cut prior to its draping to ensure that all the material stays within the mould. The shape of the fabric blank depends on the part shape and on the orientation of the fabric. From a simulation involving “extra” fabric (Figure 5), it is possible to determine the ideal geometry of the fabric blank. A second simulation using a properly sized blank can validate the blank shape. An example is given in Figure 7. The use of a blank adapted to the part geometry and fabric orientation permits a slight reduction of the shear angles, e.g. compare the upper right corner of the tub in Figures 5b and 7b.

Figure 7. Determination of the blank geometry. (a) Fabric blank geometry. (b) Final shape after forming showing shear angle contour in degrees.

CONCLUSION

In this study, SMC molding of prepreg fiberglass woven fabric was considered to form structural automotive parts. First, the SMC fabric was characterized, in terms of tensile, in-plane shear and frictional behaviours to determine a set of material parameters for the model. Finite element simulations were run to study the forming of an actual part. It has been shown that shear angles are a function of the fabric orientation and that a $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation results in lower shear angles than a $90^\circ/0^\circ$ orientation for the part considered. Both fabric orientations exhibit locally very high tension in the yarns, denoting risks of tearing. The simulation can be used to determine the appropriate shape of the blank as a function of the part geometry and fabric orientation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank The National Science Foundation (NSF Grant # DMI-0331267), U.S. Department of Energy, Ford Motor Company and General Motors for partial support of this research and the partial support from USCAR Automotive Composites Consortium.

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